

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS
ON THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF GLASS CLOTH/EPOXY
AND GRAPHITE FIBER/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this paper is to characterize the fracture behavior of laminated composites by applying the concepts of linear elastic fracture mechanics. The fracture toughness of glass cloth/epoxy and graphite fiber/epoxy laminates is studied by the use of three different techniques including K-calibration, J-integral and Energy method. Anisotropic effect of composites on the fracture toughness is involved by means of the author's SIFJTAP finite element program. Experimental results show that the fracture toughness of the two kinds of laminates is independent of crack length but strongly dependent on the laminate's principal elastic constants and the crack directions to the laminate's principal axis. The anisotropic theories of linear elastic fracture mechanics prove applicable to study the crack initiation failure but somewhat fail to study the crack growth and the damage development in laminated composites.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite materials have been widely utilized in aircraft structures because of their strong advantage that they can be tailor-made with the strength and stiffness oriented as needed for a specific application so that high specific strength and stiffness result. When the filamentary composites are used as structural materials,

their ultimate static strength may be sharply reduced due to the existence of initial defects, damages and cracks induced by mechanical processing and shooting. The aircraft structures require a high degree of safety thus it is necessary to have a thorough comprehension of fracture phenomena in composites.

The concepts of linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) have been successfully applied to isotropic materials such as metals. For a number of reasons, these concepts are currently being used to composite materials. The fundamentals and applicabilities of LEFM to composites were discussed by Smith and Mullinix [1] and Parhizgar et al. [2]. The current study is to estimate the fracture behavior of laminated composites by utilizing the anisotropic theories of LEFM and emphasis will especially be on the investigation of the fracture toughness of laminated composites.

Some previous investigators used K-calibration technique of metal fracture toughness tests to estimate the fracture toughness for composites and neglected anisotropic effect of composites on the fracture toughness. For the reason Parhizgar et al. [2] developed a Solid Sap finite element program to take the effect into account for the purpose of the application of the K-calibration technique to composite fracture toughness tests. Parhizgar's work and Sih's analysis [3] also showed that there would exist mixed-mode displacements in the vicinity of crack tip in anisotropic materials thus both mode I and mode II stress intensity factors occurred in spite of geometrical and loading symmetry of the anisotropic material specimens.

In this paper, the fracture toughness of glass-cloth/epoxy and graphite-fiber/epoxy laminates is determined by the experiments of the standard compact tension specimens with different crack lengths and for different crack directions to laminate's principal axis. K-calibration, J-integral and Energy methods are used to estimate the laminated composite fracture toughness. Anisotropic effect is taken into account in the K-calibration and J-integral approaches by using the authors' SIFJTAP finite element program which is capable of handling anisotropic eight-noded isoparametric elements.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

Two kinds of laminated composite materials were used which are 3240 glass-cloth reinforced epoxy laminate(3240) and $[0_2/\pm 45/\pm 45/0_2]_S$ graphite fiber reinforced epoxy laminate (C/E). The laminates can be considered as orthotropic homogeneous materials by the use of classical lamination theory. Determination of the principal elastic constants for 3240 and C/E composites was fulfilled by utilizing strain gages attached to standard tension specimens(strips) subjected to tensile along the two principal axes and at a angle of 45° to the principal axis. The elastic constants are listed in the following table.

TABLE 1
Elastic constants of 3240 and C/E laminates

Materials	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	B(mm)	Fiber Volume
3240	24.52	22.56	4.10	0.16	8.4	45%
C/E	58.45	19.22	15.49	0.61	2.2	60%

Note: B means laminate thickness

The standard compact tension specimen(CT specimen) has been widely used in fracture toughness tests of metals and here is generalized to composites. Configuration of the CT specimen is coincident with ASTM E399-81 standard[4] and is shown in Figure 1 where a is crack length, W specimen width, and θ the angle between crack line and the laminate's principal axis 1. For all CT specimens tested, W is equal to 50mm and B , specimen thickness, is dependent on the laminate's thickness as shown in Figure 1. For 3240 specimens, cracks are oriented at angles of $\theta=0^\circ$ and $\theta=45^\circ$ and for C/E specimens $\theta=0^\circ$ and $\theta=90^\circ$, respectively. A variety of specimens with different crack lengths, $a/W=0.4, 0.5, 0.6$, were prepared. For each crack length, at least three specimens were tested. The crack tip of 3240 CT specimens was sharpened by using a

jeweler's saw and razor blades, and that of C/E CT specimens by electrospark wire-electrode cutting. These specimens were not fatigue precracked since fatigue precracking can cause damage at the crack tip than crack extension thus yielding a more blunt crack than that obtained as the result of machining.

Figure 1. Configuration of CT specimens

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The standard testing method for composite fracture toughness tests is not available. It is difficult to obtain the fracture toughness of composites in the same way as is used for metallic materials. Because in the case of composites there are no standards for verifying toughness validity or K_{IC} status, the K_Q notation was used to denote a composite's fracture toughness which only means geometrically independent.

Fracture toughness tests for 3240 and C/E CT specimens were conducted in INSTRON 1251 materials testing machine. The tests are considered quasi-static since the displacement rate of the testing machine's cross-head is at 1 mm/min.. YJ-0540 clip gage was utilized to measure the crack-opening displacement at the load line. It was necessary to constrain the C/E CT specimens to prevent out-of-plane bending, which was done by clamping 5mm thick lubricated steel plates to both sides

of the specimen. The specimen in-plane compliance was unaffected but out-of-plane deformation was satisfactorily limited.

The critical load, P_Q , was determined based on the load versus crack-opening displacement curve ($P-\delta$ curve) for a specimen thus the critical stress intensity factor (SIF), K_Q , and the critical J-integral, J_Q , can be established in combination with the three techniques as following.

K-Calibration

The K-calibration formula for CT specimens is given by

$$K_i = PY_i / (BW^{\frac{1}{2}}) \quad i=I, II \quad (1)$$

where P is the load applied to CT specimen, Y_i ($i=I, II$) mode I and mode II calibration factors. When the load reaches P_Q , K_Q can be obtained from Eq. (1). The calibration factors are not only dependent on the specimen configuration but also dependent on the elastic constants of composites. Therefore, they can not be calculated from the calibration formula presented in ASTM E399-81 standard for metallic materials. A finite element program, SIFJTAP, which is capable of handling anisotropic eight-noded isoparametric elements and their collapsed forms, i.e. $\frac{1}{4}$ -point triangular singular elements, was developed to compute the calibration factors [5]. The calibration factors of 3240 and C/E CT specimens with different crack lengths and crack directions are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2
Calibration factors of 3240 and C/E CT specimens

Mat.	θ	$Y_I, K\text{-calibration}$			$Y_I, J\text{-integral}^*$			$Y_{II}, K\text{-calib.}$		
		a/W=0.4	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.6
3240	0°	7.38	9.56	13.32	7.38	9.55	13.32	---	---	---
3240	45°	7.42	9.92	14.13	7.41	9.90	14.09	.26	.34	.57
C/E	0°	6.82	9.32	13.52	6.80	9.29	13.47	---	---	---
C/E	90°	8.59	10.75	14.46	8.58	10.73	14.43	---	---	---

* Normalized J-integral, $Y_I = (J_I E' W)^{\frac{1}{2}} / P$

When $\theta=45^\circ$ that crack line is not parallel to any laminate's principal axes, crack tip displacements are mixed thus

mode I and mode II SIFs exist simultaneously (Table 2). The critical mode II SIF, K_{IIQ} , can be also estimated combined P_Q and Eq.(1).

J-Integral

Rice's J-integral is used for estimating the fracture toughness of composites and is rewritten below

$$J_I = \int_{\Gamma} w dy - \vec{T} \cdot \partial \vec{u} / \partial x ds \quad (2)$$

where J_I is computed by using SIFJTAP program. The normalized results of J_I of 3240 and C/E CT specimens are also shown in Table 2. When $P=P_Q$, we have $J_I=J_{IQ}$. The K_{IQ} equivalent to the J_{IQ} is given by means of the following relation [5]

$$K_{IQ} = (J_{IQ} E')^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where E' is material's constant established in terms of elastic constants and crack directions.

Energy Method

Integrating the area under $P-\delta$ curve of CT specimen, we have the energy absorbed in the specimen during loading

$$U = \int_0^{\delta} P d\delta \quad (4)$$

J-integral is related to U in form of [6]

$$J_I = 2U / (B(W-a)) \cdot (1 - \frac{1}{2}(W-a)/(W+a)) \quad (5)$$

Apparently, as soon as P_Q is known, J_{IQ} and the equivalent K_{IQ} can be determined according to Eq.(5) and Eq.(3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows two typical load versus crack-opening displacement curves of 3240 and C/E CT specimens with $a/W=0.5$. In the figure, P_e means the limit proportional load, P_f the load when either a smooth segment of $P-\delta$ curve (with reference to the start of subcritical crack growth in 3240 laminate) or a "saw-tooth shaped" piece of $P-\delta$ curve (relevant to the development of damages such as fiber-matrix debonding and delamina-

tion at crack tip in C/E laminate) first appears, and P_m the maximum load relevant to the highest point of $P-\delta$ curve. The assumption that laminated composites are considered linearly elastic, anisotropic and homogeneous will hold until the load reaches P_f when the damage zone in the vicinity of crack tip is limited to a small region and crack is about to extend. Therefore, LEFM can still work to characterize the fracture behavior of laminates at the load P_f . In the following study, P_f is considered corresponding to the start of crack growth and therefore as the critical load, P_Q , for determining two fracture toughness parameters, K_Q and J_Q .

In additional, K_{Im} and J_{Im} corresponding to P_m are also given below in order to estimate the applicability of LEFM to composite laminates after the start of crack extension.

Figure 2. Typical load versus crack-opening displacement of CT specimen with $a/W=0.5$

3240 Specimens

K_Q and J_Q of 3240 CT specimens are shown in Table 3. It is seen that both K_{IQ} and J_{IQ} for $\theta=0^\circ$ and 45° somewhat decrease with increasing a/W . However, the K_{IQ} for each a/W only has a maximum difference (MDM) of 5% to the average (MEAN) of K_{IQ} s for different crack lengths and the MDM for J_{IQ} is not more than 9%. Therefore, the K_{IQ} and J_{IQ} are considered

independent of crack length and as the fracture toughness of 3240 composites.

TABLE 3
Fracture toughness of 3240 composite

θ	0°					45°				
	a/W 0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN	MDM	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN	MDM
P_Q	4737	3599	2432			4717	3540	2295		
K_{I1Q}	18.80	18.44	17.45	18.23	4	18.51	18.53	17.37	18.13	4
K_{I2Q}	18.77	18.49	17.39	18.21	5	18.49	18.59	17.32	18.13	5
K_{I3Q}	20.20	19.58	19.09	19.62	3	18.96	19.14	18.12	18.74	3
K_{I1Q}^1	---	---	---			0.65	0.64	0.70	0.66	6
J_{I2Q}^2	20.85	20.21	17.90	19.65	9	19.81	20.07	17.38	19.09	9
J_{I3Q}^3	24.25	22.68	21.57	22.84	6	20.71	21.33	19.03	20.36	7

Note: P_Q , K_Q and J_Q in N, $\text{MPam}^{\frac{1}{2}}$, and kPam , respectively;
Superscripts 1, 2, 3 of K_Q et al. means K-calibration,
J-integral and Energy method, respectively.

Table 3 shows that the results from K-calibration and J-integral approaches are similar but little more different from those of Energy method, which partly proves that K_Q and J_Q are equivalent for the laminated composites under the sense of LEFM; K-calibration is identical with J-integral. The K_Q of Energy method is calculated based on the area under P- δ curve which partly involves the nonlinear effect of composites and thus is larger than those of the other methods. The following report only gives the results from K-calibration and Energy techniques.

The maximum SIF and J-integral, K_{Im} and J_{Im} relevant to P_m are shown in Table 4. A white triangular damage zone at crack tip in 3240 specimens was observed for the case that the load increases to P_f and then the damage zone smoothly extends with the increase of loading until the load reaches P_m after which a sharp drop of the load is followed and the specimen is unloaded. Because of better ply-up the delamination in 3240 specimens is not serious. That the ratio P_m/P_Q is approximately equal to unity implies that no sooner had the sub-

critical crack growth started than the instable crack growth occurred. The damage region in 3240 CT specimens is very small and the K_{Im} and J_{Im} might also be referred to as fracture resistance parameters in the sense of LEFM.

TABLE 4

K_{Im} and J_{Im} of 3240 laminate CT specimens

θ	0°					45°				
	a/W	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN MDM	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN MDM	
P_m	4844	3805	2540			4903	3657	2461		
P_m/P_Q	1.023	1.057	1.040			1.040	1.033	1.073		
K_{Im}^1	19.23	19.51	18.15	18.96	4	19.24	19.26	18.67	19.05	2
K_{Im}^2	22.45	21.64	21.12	21.74	3	20.65	20.84	21.04	20.84	1
J_{Im}^3	29.81	27.74	26.38	27.98	7	24.71	25.18	26.65	25.18	2

C/E Specimens

Two crack orientations of C/E specimens are along the two principal axes of elasticity and therefore only mode I fracture toughness parameters need determining. The K_{IQ} and J_{IQ} of C/E CT specimens are tabulated in Table 5. From the table we observed that the K_{IQ} and J_{IQ} are independent of specimen crack lengths but strongly dependent on the crack directions and for each fixed angle θ the fracture toughness of C/E composite is a constant material property independent of crack lengths.

Among metallic materials, the higher a kind of metal's strength, the lower the fracture toughness. For composites, the principle works no longer. Generally, the composite with higher strength will have higher fracture toughness.

TABLE 5

Fracture toughness for C/E CT specimens

θ	0°					90°				
	a/W	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN MDM	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN MDM	
P_Q	1363	1079	716			2795	2148	1540		
K_{IQ}^1	19.24	19.52	19.02	19.26	1	46.88	46.40	44.07	45.78	4
K_{IQ}^2	21.46	21.10	21.09	21.22	1	50.97	52.87	50.25	51.37	4
J_{IQ}^3	16.91	16.38	16.33	16.53	2	55.18	58.92	53.25	55.78	6

Table 6 gives the maximum SIF and J-integral, K_{Im} and J_{Im} , of C/E CT specimens. The K_{Im} and J_{Im} change with a/W more greatly than those of 3240 specimens did because the damage such as debonding and delamination in C/E specimens was much heavier than that of 3240 specimens. In fact, when the load applied to C/E CT specimens reaches P_m , the damage around crack tip has occupied a considerable region. Whether so-called fracture parameters, K_{Im} and J_{Im} have the sense of LEFM is worth being more deeply investigated.

TABLE 6
 K_{Im} and J_{Im} for C/E CT specimens

θ	0°					90°				
	a/W	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN MDM	0.4	0.5	0.6	MEAN MDM	
P_m		1393	1206	804		2971	2393	1952		
P_m/P_Q		1.022	1.118	1.123		1.063	1.114	1.268		
K_{Im}^1		19.67	21.93	21.52	21.04 7	49.90	51.73	56.00	52.54 7	
K_{Im}^2		23.56	25.86	28.16	25.86 9	58.88	65.55	68.95	64.29 9	
J_{Im}^3		20.63	24.81	29.22	24.89 17	72.31	90.61	100.7	87.87 18	

Compared with 3240 specimens, C/E specimens have more complicated fracture phenomena when the load is more than P_f . The compression failure due to bending stress in the specimen edge in front of the main direction of damage zone development. The compression failure and the damage mechanism after crack initial growth in C/E specimens are under investigated.

CONCLUSIONS

Several important observations were made and discussed regarding the applicability of LEFM to 3240 glas-cloth/epoxy laminate and $[0_2/\pm 45/\pm 45/0_2]_s$ graphite-fiber/epoxy laminate. First, experimental results show that LEFM is applicable to study the crack initiation failure of laminated composites as long as the fracture characteristics and the anisotropic effect of the laminates are involved. For 3240 material, LEFM

gives reasonable results of studying both the crack initiation failure and the ultimate failure relevant to the maximum load. For C/E laminate, LEFM only presents conservative results because of the complex damage failure zone which develops in lieu of a sharp crack.

Second, the fracture toughness of both 3240 and C/E composites is independent of crack lengths for each fixed crack orientations but strongly dependent on the elastic constants of the laminated composites. Therefore, the K_Q of 3240 and C/E composite is a crack-direction-dependent material property.

Finally, for the two kinds of laminated composite materials tested, two fracture toughness parameters, K_Q and J_Q are equivalent and both of them can represent the fracture resistance of composite materials. The K-calibration and J-integral techniques in the paper are identical.

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